

First Survey and Characterization Report of *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates in North Sinai for Bayoud Disease Presence

AbdAllah, S. M.^{*1,2}, Abdalla, M.Y.³, Sourour, M. M.¹.

¹ Faculty of Environmental Agricultural Sciences, Arish University, Egypt

² College of Agriculture, Health, and Natural Resources, University of Connecticut, USA

³ Faculty of Desert and Environmental Agriculture, Matrouh University, Egypt

Abstract:- One of the most severe and challenging plant pathogens is the *Fusarium* genre because of its ability to the complex fermentation and fermentation process of plant cell walls by its unique and fatal enzyme system that stimulates fungi to infect, adapt, and survive anaerobically or aerobically worldwide, especially, in the middle east region due to the importance of the date fruit for the natives. A total of 625 *Fusarium* sp. isolates were collected for the first time from four different geographic regions in North Sinai. Trees and offshoots of varieties Hayany, Samany, Bent Easha, and Medjhooh showed foliar disease symptoms e.g., wilt, drying, chlorosis, and progressive dieback. Root samples showed internal red dye, fermentation, and ethanol scent. Symptoms were comparable with those caused by *F. oxysporum* Schl. f.sp. *albedinis* (Foa). Pathogen isolates were characterized macroscopically, microscopically, and molecularly with specific primers for detecting Foa. Most of them were *F. oxysporum* isolates. After being tested primer pairs (FOA₁-BIO₃ and FOA₂₈-TL₃) on regions representative samples as described were specific to a long terminal repeat (LTR, i.e., terminals of the transposable element Fot₁) which was previously detected in the *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis*, only the primer FOA₂₈ & TL₃ was successful in amplifying from the genomic DNA of 13 isolates.

Keywords:- *Fusarium*, Bayoud Disease, Date Palm, Dieback, Molecular Characterization, Phylogenetic, Necrosis, Sinai.

I. INTRODUCTION

Date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) plays an important role in Egyptian agriculture and represents a significant part of the reclamation program. Besides the nutritional values and health benefits of the fruits, the date palm by-products are daily used by Egyptians Bekheet and El-Sharabasy (2015). The ability of date palm trees to acclimate to drought has positioned it as one of the initial fruit-bearing trees that were disseminated and introduced into cultivation in arid and semi-arid areas of Egypt, it has numerous cultivars of dates that are extensively distributed for economic profits. (Sami et al., 2014). The demand for date fruit has increased recently in the traditional growing areas additionally world widely driven by rising awareness of

health benefits (FAO, 2023). The general production of date fruit in Egypt is around 1,8 million metric tons (FAO, 2021). As much as 30% of fruit production can potentially be lost because of pests and disease, exceptionally, soilborne pathogens like *Alternaria alternata*, *Diplodia phoenicum*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, and *Fusarium* strains. (Loutfy, 2010). *Fusarium* diseases are recorded leaf spots, blights, yellowing, inflorescence rot, fruit rot, root rot, and death of mature and young trees (Tsutomu, 2019). In Saudi Arabia, *F. oxysporum* has the highest genetic diversity and stability toward the surrounding ecological changes comparing to other *Fusarium* species and pathogens that affect positively on mycelial growth and the pathogenicity index Saleh et al., (2021). *Fusarium* fungi on the top of global cereal crops by the complex mycotoxins and enzyme systems especially glucose catabolism and pentose phosphate (Anasontzis et al., 2016) (Tulin, 2018). *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis* is the deadliest species in the *Fusarium* genre, it has distinguished characteristics that enable it to spread rapidly and cause losses of over three million date palm trees in Moroccan and Algerian lands, additionally, it spreads eastward without enough research coverage (Benzohra et al., 2015). Bayoud is a significant danger and constraint on date palm nurseries and farms in North-western Africa and other countries with a high percentage occurrence in the future. Foa has wide range of conditions to survive and produce three kinds of spores (Macroconidia, microconidia, and chlamydoconidia) that boost its intracellular and intercellular penetration (Belarbi-Halli and Mangenot, 2011). Plants are equipped with multirole defense systems one of the most effective against the majority of pathogens' toxins strategies is growth regulators e.g., salicylic acid, cytokinin, and ethylene (Dinolfo et al., 2017). Although the induced resistance and self-defending processes at all stages started from preliminary respond (invasion start), infection process, and full conquer (post infection) by many phytohormones, still a myriad of economically crops are vulnerable to pathogens attacks, which is driven to apply the chemical approaches and dealing with the secondary environmental complex problems in return to save final profitable yield (Abd Allah et al., 2016). The last decade of twentieth century, phenetic analysis of species was applied on *Fusarium* to deep more under the traditional detecting surface that pointed new species of *Fusarium* which was

hardly to belong in with old-fashioned characterization sets (Tulin, 2018).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Fungal Isolates Collecting

The survey covered 2- 4 farms per district, with 5-10 date palm trees in each farm. Root samples were collected from trees showing wilt symptoms at 30 – 100 cm deep. Root samples were rinsed in running tap water for about 10 min. Roots were then cut into pieces 10 cm long, soaked for 1-2 min in 0.5% sodium hypochlorite solution (NaOCl), rinsed in sterile distilled water (SDW), and placed on acidified potato dextrose agar (APDA) with pH=5. Plates were incubated at 25°C for 2 weeks.

B. Morphological Characterization

Developed fungal growth was purified and identified on morphological and characteristics (Alexopoulos and Mims, 1979); (Barnett and Hunter, 1972); (Ashar et al., 2023). A) For macroscopic observation, a mycelial disc of 5mm diameter was transferred and inoculated centrally onto APDA plates (90mm diameter) and incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The colony appearance and pigmentations were assessed since the isolates started on growth. The macroscopic characteristics such as colony appearance (texture and color of aerial mycelium, colony pigmentations and growth rate). Colony color and pigmentation were determined by using Methuen handbook of color chart (Kornerup and Wancher, 1978), while growth rate was measured weekly until the fungal growth covered the whole plate. For microscopic characterization, the isolates were cultured on APDA for 2 to 4 weeks. Determined characteristics were (the shapes of macroconidia and microconidia, length and width of macroconidia and microconidia, macroconidia septation and presence or absence of chlamydoconidia). (Booth, 1977), (Nelson et al. 1983), (Leslie and Summerell, 2006).

C. Pathogenicity Tests

➤ Plant Preparation

Two hundred seeds of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. variety (Hayany) were used in this study. The seeds were washed carefully with tap water to remove the remainder fruit particles and were surface sterilized using 1% sodium hypochlorite solution for 2 minutes, washed with tap water again for 5 minutes (Barka et al., 2011); (Abdellah et al., 2023). The seeds were treated with sodium hydroxide solution 10% for 10 minutes and soaked in tap water for 5 days to activate germination, then planted in black plastic bags, filled with a mixture of equal portions of sand and peat moss. Pots were kept in the greenhouse and watered periodically thirty days until seedlings emerged (Eletmany et al, 2017, 2018,2019, 2023).

➤ Fungal Inocula

Autoclaved wheat grain medium, in 500 ml conical flasks approximately containing 200 gm of wheat then added SDW water to approximately the 300 ml level. Flasks were autoclaved for 15minutes, inoculated with 1 cm disc of the tested fungus. Inoculated wheat grain was incubated at

$25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and shaken at least twice a day, until the materials were completely colonized; usually 14-21 days Woo (1996); Leslie and Summerell (2006). The inoculum of each pathogen was air-dried for twenty-four hours in a laminar flow hood. The inoculum of each pathogen was added to the previously described pots at the rate of 5% of soil weight and mixed well; pots were then covered with black plastic bags for 24 hr., to maintain high humidity. Irrigation was carried out regularly five times a week to ensure even distribution of the inoculated fungi in the soil. Symptoms were recorded after six months depending on the range of wilt and yellowing of leaves on a scale from 0 to 4 according to Grattidge and O'Brien (1982) and Abdalla et al., (2000), visible symptoms on each seedling where:0, (0–24%) of leaves yellowed and wilted; 1, (25–49%) of leaves yellowed and wilted; 2, (50–74%) of leaves yellowed and wilted; 3, (75–99%) of leaves yellowed and wilted; 4, (100%) dead plant. Scores were computed to determine the disease severity index (DSI) where; $DSI = \frac{\sum (\text{seedlings/class} \times \text{class score})}{\text{total seedlings}}$. All experiments were conducted in completely randomized design (CRD). Mean values were compared by the least significant difference (LSD) testing at $p = 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed using Co-STAT software V.6.13 (CoHort software, Berkeley, CA 94701). Also, EC50 uses LDP-Line and GW-BASIC (Version 3.23 from Microsoft®).

D. Molecular Characterization

➤ Fungal Materials

Isolates were grown on APDA medium at 25°C for 7 days. The mycelium was collected into Eppendorf tubes by scraping with a sterile spatula. Fungal genomic DNA was extracted using a mini-preparation method. One milliliter of extraction buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH: 7.5, 50 mM EDTA, 3% SDS) was added and the samples were incubated for 60 min at 65°C, and then centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 1 min and discard supernatant. After adding equal volume of phenol–chloroform, the mixture was centrifuged again. The DNA was precipitated with 0.5 volume of 7.5 mM ammonium acetate and 1.5 volume of isopropanol. The pellet was rinsed with ethanol, suspended in TE buffer, pH 7.4 and stored at -20°C .

➤ Molecular Marker Analysis

Grounded mycelia were resuspended in 700 μL of hexacetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB; Jena Bioscience, Germany) extraction buffer [100 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.4), 1.4 M NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, 2% CTAB] and vortexed for 10 sec. The homogenate was incubated at 65°C for 30 min. Following extraction, an equal volume of chloroform was added to the mixture, vortexed for 5 sec and then spun for 10 min at 13,000 rpm and 4°C. Subsequently, 500 μL portion of the upper phase was transferred into a new 1.5 mL tube and 5 μL of RNaseA (20 mg/mL) was added to the tube. The mixture was incubated at 37°C for 30 min. DNA was precipitated with an addition of equal volume of isopropanol and kept for 15 min at -20°C . After the DNA was pelleted by centrifuging at 13,000 rpm for 1 min, the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was

gently washed with 70% ethanol and resuspended in 20 µL distilled water. The DNA was stored at –20°C.

After a wash with 70% ethanol, the pellet was vacuum dried for five minutes and re-suspended in 50 µL of TE (200 mM Tris HCl pH 8.5, 250 mM NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, 0.5% SDS). The amount of DNA obtained in this way was a rounded 3-6 ng. The primers for *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp.albedinis (Foa) specific amplification included two primer pairs: FOA1 (CAGTTTATTAGAAATGCCGCC - 3' flanking) coupled with BIO3 (GGCGATCTTGATTGTATTGTGGTG - 3' end) with amplicon size (bp) 204 and FOA28 (ATCCCCGTAAAGCCCTGAAGC-5' flanking) coupled with TL3 (GGTCGTCCGCAGAGTATACCGGC - 5' end) with amplicon size (bp) 400 Fernandez et al. (1998); S. Freeman and Maymon (2000) PCR (Thermo Hybaiel) was conducted in a 20 µL reaction volume. Each reaction mixture contained 2 µL 10X buffer solution with MgCl₂, 0.5 µL 10 mM dNTP, 2 µL of 10 mM primers, 2 units of taq DNA polymerase) Jena Bioscience, Germany(and 2 µL of DNA template (50 – 100ng), and the volume was made up to 20 µL with double-distilled sterile water cycling

parameters were: 94°C for 1 minute, 50°C for 1 minute and 55°C for 2 minutes, for 35 cycles and a final auto-extension step of 72°C for 5 minutes. The amplified product was analyzed by gel electrophoresis on a 1.5% agarose gel containing 10 mg/ml of ethidium bromide and visualized under UV light. Cenis (1992); Noor Adila et al. (2007); Zhao et al. (2014).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Collection of Samples

The results in (Table 1) showed that the pathogens isolated represented nine species of six genre i.e. *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium solani*, *Fusarium proliferatum*, *Fusarium* spp., *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Thielaviopsis paradoxa*, *Diplodia phoenicum* and *Cephalosporium* sp., these species were identified according to the morphological, culture characteristics and microscopical characters as described by Booth (1977), Gerlach and Nirenberg (1982), Nelson et al. (1983), Burgess et al. (1994), Leslie and Summerell (2006) and Barnett and Hunter (1972).

Table 1 The Percentage of Pathogenic Fungi Isolated from Roots of Diseased Date Palm from Locations (Rafah, Al Shaikh Zawayed, Al Arish, and Bear Al Abd) in North Sinai Governorate During 2012 and 2013.

Fungi	Rafah No. of isolates	Al Shaikh Zawayed No. of isolates	Al Arish No. of isolates	Bear Al-Abd No. of isolates	Mean No. of isolates
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	27	38	137	169	371
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp	-	-	-	12	12
<i>Diplodia phoenicum</i>	-	23	76	109	208
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	16	12	113	117	258
<i>Fusarium proliferatum</i>	17	18	32	-	67
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	-	-	41	37	78
<i>Fusarium</i> sp	18	28	91	85	222
<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	-	64	137	139	340
<i>Thielaviopsis paradoxa</i>	-	32	88	105	225

B. Macroscopic Characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates

Colony morphology of *F. oxysporum* isolates on APDA at 25°C varied widely. Growth on APDA appeared as soft, delicate, cottony, abundant, or poor growth. The color ranged from white to pale violet, white-creamy, violet, violet to peach and magenta. Data presented in (Table 2) & (Plate 1 and 2) indicated that, all 25 isolates could be divided into six groups based on colony type.

➤ Group A:

Consisted of isolates (A₁, G₁ and I₂), these isolates were white in colony color and the colonies texture was floccose for isolates (A₁ - I₂) and abundant-cottony for isolate (G₁). Growth rate was 60, 80 and 63 mm/week for isolates (A₁ - G₁ - I₂) respectively. Isolates in this group produced white-creamy and white-creamy to beige pigmentation.

➤ Group B:

Consisted of isolates (A₂, C₃₈, D₁, F₃₃ and F₄₈), this group produced colonies that were white to pale violet in color, the colonies textures were generally floccose, but

isolates (F₃₃ and F₄₈) had felt texture with growth rate approximately: 60 - 65 mm/week. Isolates in this group produced violet pigmentation.

➤ Group C:

Consisted of isolates (A₅, C₁, C₃₃, F₇, F₁₉, F₄₅, F₅₃, F₅₈ and H₁) this group produced colonies that were white to pale violet, but isolates (F₅₃ and H₁) were white creamy and white respectively in color. The colonies textures were generally abundant-floccose except isolate A₅ which had poor and flat growth, with growth rate about 50 mm/week while isolates (C₁, C₃₃, F₇, F₁₉, F₄₅, F₅₃, F₅₈ and H₁) had growth rate of 55 - 74 mm/week. Isolates in this group produced peach to violet pigmentation.

➤ Group D:

Consisted of isolates (A₆, C₁₂ and C₂₄), this group produced colonies that were white to pale violet in color. The colonies texture was generally floccose but isolates A₆ showed fast and heavy growth with growth rate 73 mm/week. Isolates (C₁₂ and C₂₄) had a growth rate of 58 - 61 mm/week. This group produced pale violet pigments.

➤ *Group E:*

Consisted of two isolates (B2 and D2), this group produced colonies that were violet for isolate B2 and pale violet for isolate D2. The colonies texture was abundant-cottony for isolates B2 but floccose for isolate D2, with growth rate 70 mm/week. This group produced magenta pigments.

➤ *Group F:*

Consisted of isolates (B1, B7 and E1) this group produced colonies that were peach in color. The colonies texture was abundant-floccose, with growth rate 72-75 mm/week. This group produced peach pigment.

Table 2 Macroscopic Characteristics of *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates Associated with Collected Date Palm Roots in North Sinai.

Group	Isolates No.	Colony texture	Colony color	Colony pigmentation	Growth rate (mm / week)
A	A ₁	Floccose	White	White-creamy to beige	60.00
	G ₁	Abundant – floccose	White	White-creamy	80.00
	I ₂	Floccose	White	White-creamy	63.00
B	A ₂	Floccose	White to pale violet	Violet	60.00
	C ₃₈	Floccose	White to pale violet	Violet	65.00
	D ₁	Floccose	White to pale violet	Violet	65.00
	F ₃₃	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Violet	65.00
	F ₄₈	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Violet	63.00
C	A ₅	Poor – flat	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	50.00
	C ₁	Floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	55.00
	C ₃₃	Floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	57.00
	F ₇	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	68.00
	F ₁₉	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	65.00
	F ₄₅	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	66.00
	F ₅₃	Abundant - floccose	White creamy	Peach to violet	70.00
	F ₅₈	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	Peach to violet	70.00
D	H ₁	Abundant - floccose	White	Peach to violet	74.00
	A ₆	Abundant - floccose	White to pale violet	pale violet	73.00
	C ₁₂	Floccose	White to pale violet	pale violet	61.00
E	C ₂₄	Floccose	White to pale violet	pale violet	58.00
	B ₂	Abundant - floccose	Violet	Magenta	70.00
I	D ₂	Floccose	pale violet	Magenta	70.00
	B ₁	Abundant - floccose	Peach	Peach to red	72.00
	B ₇	Abundant - floccose	Peach	Peach to red	75.00
	E ₁	Abundant - floccose	Peach	Peach to red	75.00

Plate 1 Macroscopic characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (A1, A2, A5, A6, B1, B2, B7, C1, C12, C24, C33 and C38) from diseased date palm trees from three different districts in Bear Al Abd.

Plate 2 Macroscopic characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (D1, D2) from diseased date palm trees isolated from Rafah and isolate (E1) from Al Shaikh Zewayed, while isolates (F7, F19, F33, F45, F48, F53, and F58) and isolates (G1, H1 and I2) from Al Arish.

C. Microscopic Characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates

All isolates were morphologically similar in producing conidia on short monophialides in false head (Plate 3E-F) on the aerial mycelium.

Chlamydospores formed abundantly and quickly (2-4 weeks), they formed singly or in pairs. Sometimes there were either terminal or intercalary in aerial, submerged, or surface hyphae, they appeared smooth or rough walled (Plate 3D).

Microconidia of all isolates were abundant in the aerial mycelium and oval, elliptical to kidney shaped, length and width of microconidia ranged $2-3.5 \times 4-9.4 \mu\text{m}$.

➤ (Plate 3C).

Macroconidia were less in number than microconidia. Borne on branched conidiophores, short to medium length, straight to slightly curved, relatively slender and thin walled. Macroconidia in isolates (A₁, A₂, A₅, B₂, C₁, C₃₈, D₁, D₂, E₁, F₁₉, F₃₃, F₄₅, F₅₈ and I₂) were slightly curved with tapered curved apical.

Cell addition to foot shaped basal cell. These macroconidia were more similar in width and length $4-4.4 \mu\text{m} \times 32.8-36.5 \mu\text{m}$. The macroconidial septation of these isolates was generally 3 septa except isolate C₃₈ which had 5 septa.

Macroconidia in isolates (B₇ and G₁) were widely curved with tapered, curved apical cell and pointed basal cell. These macroconidia were more similar in width and length $4-4.4 \mu\text{m} \times 32.8-36.5 \mu\text{m}$. (Plate 3A-B). The macroconidial septation of these isolates was generally 3 septa (Plate 3A-B).

Macroconidia in isolates (B₁, A₆, F₅₃ and H₁) were straight and relatively slender “narrow” in shape and tapered with slightly hook apical cell and foot-shaped basal cell. Majority of these isolates were $3.4-3.9 \mu\text{m} \times 43.3-47.5 \mu\text{m}$. The macroconidial septation of these isolates was mostly 5 septa.

Macroconidia in isolates (C₁₂, C₃₃ and F₄₈) were straight and relatively slender “narrow” in shape, with tapered curved apical cell and pointed basal cell. Majority of these isolates were $3.4-3.9 \mu\text{m} \times 43.3-47.5 \mu\text{m}$. The macroconidial septation of these isolates was generally 5 septa.

The isolates (F₇ and C₂₄) were straight and relatively slender “narrow” in shape with tapered curved apical cell while basal cell was foot shaped. Majority of these isolates were $3.4-3.9 \mu\text{m} \times 43.3-47.5 \mu\text{m}$. The macroconidial septation of these isolates was mostly 5 septa. Isolates A₁, A₂, A₆, B₁, C₂₄, F₁₉, F₃₃, F₄₅, F₅₈ and G₁ (Table 3) and (Plate 3G) showed the ability to produce Pale orange sporodochia.

Plate 3 Microscopic characterization for *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates from (Rafah, Al Shaikh Zewayed, Al Arish and Bear

Al Abd) in North Sinai, **A-B**: Macroconidia” black rows” in general morphology short to medium length, straight to slightly curved, relatively slender, and thin walled, which have 3-5 septate. **C**: Microconidia; Oval, elliptical or kidney shaped and abundant in the aerial mycelium. **D**: Chlamydospores formed singly or in pairs. **E-F**: Microconidia *in situ* (on short monophialides in false heads). **G**: Pale orange sporodochia produced by tested isolates.

➤ *Pathogenicity Tests*

The pathogenicity trials for 25 fungi isolated from diseased date palm roots were performed using (six) month-old date palm seedlings cultivar Hayany under greenhouse conditions during two seasons. Data was recorded 1 to 6 months after inoculation as disease severity index (DSI) as suggested by Abdalla (1986; 2000). Data in (Table 4) and (Plate 4) revealed that the isolates B₂ and F₇ ranked as the most virulent isolate with DSI of 3.48 after 6 months, followed by the isolates A₆ and F₃₃ which had a DSI of 3.10 after 6 months while the isolates A₂ and A₅ proved to be the least virulent at DSI of 2.35 after 6 months.

Table 3 Microscopic Characteristics of *Fusarium oxysporum* Tested Isolates Associated with Collected Date Palm Roots in North Sinai.

Isolates code	Macroconidia						Microconidia			Presence of sporodochia
	Macroconidia septation	Mean width of macroconidia (µm)	Mean length of macroconidia (µm)	Apical morphology	Basal morphology	Macroconidia morphology	Mean width of microconidia (µm)	Mean length of microconidia (µm)	Microconidia morphology	
A ₁	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
A ₂	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
A ₅	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
A ₆	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, slightly hooked	Pointed	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3	4.3 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia

B ₁	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, slightly hooked	Foot shaped	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.8 – 9.4	Kidney	abundant pale orange sporodochia
B ₂	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
B ₇	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Pointed	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
C ₁	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Kidney	non-existent
C ₁₂	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, curved	Pointed	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.8 – 9.4	Kidney	non-existent
C ₂₄	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.3 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
C ₃₃	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, slightly hooked	Pointed	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.8 – 9.4	Kidney	non-existent
C ₃₈	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2 – 3.3	4.3 - 9	Oval	non-existent
D ₁	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
D ₂	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
E ₁	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	non-existent
F ₇	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.3 - 9	Oval	non-existent
F ₁₉	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Kidney	abundant pale orange sporodochia
F ₃₃	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
F ₄₅	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia

F48	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, curved	Pointed	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.3 - 9	Oval	non-existent
F53	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, slightly hooked	Foot shaped	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.3 - 9	Oval	non-existent
F58	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
G1	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Pointed	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Oval	abundant pale orange sporodochia
H1	5 septa	3.4 – 3.9	43.3 – 47.5	Tapered, slightly hooked	Foot shaped	Straight and relatively slender “narrow”	2 – 3.3	4.8 – 9.4	Kidney	non-existent
I2	3 septa	4 – 4.4	32.8 – 36.5	Tapered, curved	Foot shaped	Slightly “wide” curved	2.2 – 3.5	4 - 9	Kidney	non-existent

No disease was observed with all isolates after one month. These results were similar to those reported by other researcher e.g. Beckman et al. (1995); Al-Hazmi et al. (1997); Olivain and Alabouvette (1997); Plyler et al. (1999); Abdalla et al. (2000); Sarhan (2001); Saad (2002); Fravel et al. (2003); Mandel et al. (2005); Leslie et al. (2006); El-Deeb et al. (2007); Chandel et al. (2010); Abul-Soad et al. (2011); Baraka et al. (2011).

Plate 4 Visible symptoms of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates wilt on Hayany seedlings under greenhouse condition: Control, Phase 0: no symptoms visible, Phase 1: small lesion (length of the lesion from 10 to 30 mm), Phase 2: medium lesion (length, 30 to 60 mm), Phase 3: large lesion (over 60 mm length), Phase 4: whole leaf blighted.

Table 4 Pathogenicity test on Hayany cultivar infected with 25 *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates from diseased date palm roots collected from Rafah, Al Shaikh Zawayed, Al Arish and Bear Al Abd.

Fungal isolates	% Disease severity on Hayany date palm (Time after inoculation)*					
	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5months	6 months
Control	00.00 a	0.10 g	0.10 f	0.10 h	0.10 h	0.10 g
A ₁	00.00 a	0.85 de	1.35 cd	1.85 de	2.23 ef	2.60 ef
A ₂	00.00 a	0.73 ef	1.23 de	1.73 ef	2.10 fg	2.35 g
A ₅	00.00 a	0.73 ef	1.10 e	1.48 g	2.10 fg	2.35 g
A ₆	00.00 a	0.98 cd	1.48 bc	2.10 bc	2.48 cd	3.10 b
B ₁	00.00 a	1.23 ab	1.48 bc	1.85 de	2.48 cd	2.85 cd
B ₂	00.00 a	1.23 ab	1.48 bc	2.23 ab	2.85 a	3.48 a
B ₇	00.00 a	1.35 a	1.60 ab	1.85 de	2.23 ef	2.98 bc
C ₁	00.00 a	0.60 f	1.23 de	1.60 fg	2.23 ef	2.48 fg
C ₁₂	00.00 a	0.60 f	1.23 de	1.73 ef	1.98 g	2.73 de
C ₂₄	00.00 a	1.23 ab	1.35 cd	1.73 ef	2.23 ef	2.48 fg
C ₃₃	00.00 a	1.10 bc	1.35 cd	1.60 fg	2.35 de	2.73 de
C ₃₈	00.00 a	0.53 f	1.23 de	1.73 ef	2.23 ef	2.73 de
D ₁	00.00 a	0.82 de	1.35 cd	1.73 ef	2.23 ef	2.48 fg
D ₂	00.00 a	0.67 ef	1.48 bc	2.10 bc	2.35 de	2.60 ef
E ₁	00.00 a	1.25 ab	1.73 a	2.10 bc	2.73 ab	2.98 bc
F ₇	00.00 a	1.39 a	1.73 a	2.35 a	2.85 a	3.48 a
F ₁₉	00.00 a	0.67 ef	1.73 a	2.23 ab	2.60 bc	2.85 cd
F ₃₃	00.00 a	1.25 ab	1.60 ab	2.10 bc	2.73 ab	3.10 b
F ₄₅	00.00 a	1.10 de	1.60 ab	2.10 bc	2.35 de	2.73 de
F ₄₈	00.00 a	0.67 ef	1.48 bc	2.23 ab	2.60 bc	2.73 de
F ₅₃	00.00 a	0.53 f	1.35 cd	1.73 ef	2.23 ef	2.73 de
F ₅₈	00.00 a	0.53 f	1.35 cd	1.98 cd	2.60 bc	2.98 bc
G ₁	00.00 a	1.25 ab	1.60 ab	1.98 cd	2.60 bc	2.85 cd
H ₁	00.00 a	1.39 a	1.73 a	2.10 bc	2.48 cd	2.85 cd
I ₂	00.00 a	0.96 cd	1.35 cd	1.85 de	2.23 ef	2.48 fg
L.S.D 0.05	00.00	0.172	0.172	0.172	0.172	0.172

* Disease severity index = Σ (seedlings/class \times class score)/total seedlings. Individual plants were rated on a scale from 0 to 4 according to visible symptoms on each seedling, where 0 = no symptoms visible, 1 = small lesion (length of the lesion from 10 to 30 mm), 2 = medium lesion (length, 30 to 60 mm), 3 = large lesion (over 60 mm length), and 4 = whole leaf blighted.

Each number represents the meaning of four replicates in the two seasons.

D. Molecular Diagnosis of *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *Albedinis*

➤ DNA Polymorphism and *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *Albedinis* Detection:

According to Fernandez et al. (1998) and Freeman et al. (2000) a PCR based protocol was established in which the amplification of the primer pair FOA₂₈ & TL₃ generated a 400 bp DNA amplicon, while the primer pair FOA₁ & BIO₃ generated a 204 bp DNA amplicon. In our study, only the primer FOA₂₈ & TL₃ was successful to amplify from the genomic DNA of A₅, B₁, B₇, C₁, C₂₄, D₂, F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, F₅₈, G₁, H₁ and I₂ isolates. Several PCR conditions diverged from the described protocol showed no amplification. However, by using the exact PCR protocol, it amplified the ~ 204 bp fragment (B₇, F₅₃ and G₁) with the lowest frequency among isolates of 0.12, the 400 bp fragment (A₅, B₁, F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, F₅₈ and I₂) with a frequency of 0.35. In addition to a 150 bp fragment (A₅, B₁, B₇, C₁, C₂₄, D₂, F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, F₅₈, H₁ and I₂) with the highest frequency of 0.49, a 300 bp fragment (A₅, B₁, F₄₅, F₅₃, G₁ and I₂), a 500 bp fragment (A₅, C₁, F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, and I₂) with a frequency of 0.23 and a 900 bp fragment (B₁, F₄₅, F₅₃, G₁ and I₂) with a frequency of 0.19 (Fig. 1) (Table 5) (Plate 5).

Plate 5 Ethidium bromide-stained 1.5% agarose gel showing results of PCR experiments with primer pairs FOA₂₈ & TL₃. Amplification products from *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis* isolates (written in gray), other *F. oxysporum* isolates (written in black), and a negative control (N), respectively; M, molecular markers size 100 bp GeneRuler Plus DNA Ladder. Bands below 100 bp are dimers.

Table 5 Polymorphic bands in *F. oxysporum* isolates using specific primer pair (FOA₂₈ & TL₃). Bands molecular weight (Mw) was approximated to the nearest value, and band frequency are indicated. *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis* isolates and the reference bands are written in bold.

Isolates	MW (bp)					
	150	200	300	400	500	900
A1	0	0	0	0	0	0
A2	0	0	0	0	0	0
A5	1	0	1	1	1	0
A6	0	0	0	0	0	0
B1	1	0	1	1	0	1
B2	0	0	0	0	0	0
B7	1	1	0	0	0	0
C1	1	0	0	0	1	0
C12	0	0	0	0	0	0
C24	1	0	0	1	0	0
C33	0	0	0	0	0	0
C38	0	0	0	0	0	0
D1	0	0	0	0	0	0
D2	1	0	0	0	0	0
E1	0	0	0	0	0	0
F7	0	0	0	0	0	0
F19	0	0	0	0	0	0
F33	0	0	0	0	0	0
F45	1	0	1	1	1	1
F48	1	0	0	1	1	0
F53	1	1	1	1	1	1
F58	1	0	0	1	0	0
G1	0	1	1	1	0	1
H1	1	0	0	0	0	0
I2	1	0	1	1	1	1
Negative	0	0	0	0	0	0
Frequency	0.46	0.12	0.23	0.35	0.23	0.19

➤ *Phylogenetic Analysis Among F. oxysporum f.sp. Albedinis Isolates*

Based on the scored bands, phylogenetic relationship was estimated for the identified *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis* isolates, the tree reflected paraphyletic group of two clades. Clustering the isolates in clades and sub-clades is an indication of high genetic diversity among the isolates. Isolates of the same group are not clustered together, which can only be explained by a high gene flow presence among sampled locations, where no isolation by distance nor environmental barriers do exist. Even though the FOA1 & BIO3 primer pair was successful in identifying the subsp. *albedinis*, the multiple bands amplification contradicts the primer pair specificity proposed by Fernandez et al. (1998) and Freeman et al. (2000). The detection of a multiple bands and different patterns is not surprising, due to the natural differences in isolation site, isolation time, isolation group (A, B, C, F, G or I), and genetic divergence (as found by the Fot1-based phylogenetic analysis and the ISSR analysis).

Fig 1 UPGMA dendrogram for the *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *albedinis* detected isolates based on the Fot1-amplification data, two clades clearly appeared where more differences were found within each clade.

As observed from the band frequency, the highest two fragments are the 150 bp (0.49) which was not cited before and the 400 bp (0.35) which is the expected fragment to be amplified using this primer pair. Consequently, the Egyptian isolates have diverged genetically from the isolates studied in Fernandez et al. (1998) and Freeman et al. (2000). This can be confirmed due to the constant mutational nature of the transposable elements of jumping to different sites, inverted, and multiplied within the same genome (Pray, 2008) that would alter the obtained results from the results found in the literature.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the macroscopic and microscopic characterizations of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates presented in this study provide valuable insights into the diversity within this pathogen. The colony morphology of these isolates exhibited a wide range of characteristics, with six distinct groups identified based on colony type, color, and texture. This diversity in colony features hints at the genetic variability and adaptation strategies of these isolates.

Microscopic analysis revealed that the isolates shared common traits, such as the production of conidia on short monophialides and the formation of chlamydospores. However, variations in the characteristics of macroconidia, including size, shape, and septation, were observed among different groups of isolates. Notably, some isolates displayed the ability to produce pale orange sporodochia.

Pathogenicity tests demonstrated varying levels of virulence among the isolates, with B2 and F7 being the most virulent and A2 and A5 the least virulent. These results highlight the importance of understanding the pathogenic potential of different isolates in the context of disease management and control.

Furthermore, the molecular diagnosis using DNA polymorphism provided insights into the genetic diversity among *F. oxysporum f.sp. albedinis* isolates. The PCR-based protocol, specifically the primer pairs FOA28 & TL3 and FOA1 & BIO3, revealed distinct amplification patterns, indicating genetic heterogeneity within the isolates. Phylogenetic analysis confirmed this diversity and suggested the presence of a high gene flow among sampled locations.

In summary, this study has contributed to a better understanding of the variability and pathogenicity of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates and highlighted the potential challenges in molecular diagnosis due to the genetic diversity within this pathogen. This knowledge is crucial for the development of effective disease management strategies in date palm cultivation. Further research and monitoring may help elucidate the underlying genetic mechanisms and facilitate the development of targeted control measures.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdalla, M.Y.; A. Al-Rokibah; A. Moretti and G. Mulè (2000). Pathogenicity of toxigenic *Fusarium proliferatum* from date palm in Saudi Arabia. *Plant Dis.*, 84: 321-324.
- [2]. AbdAllah, S. M., Abdalla, M. Y. and Sourour, M. M. (2016) Efficacy of certain fungicides and antagonistic microorganisms on mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolated from date palm in North Sinai. *Sinai Journal of Applied science* 5(2), pp.18-196.
- [3]. Alexopoulos, C. J. and C. W. Mims. (1979). *Introductory Mycology*. 3rd ed. John Wiley and Sons. New York.
- [4]. Anasontzis, G. E., Kourtoglou, E., Villas-Boas, S. G., Hatzinikolaou, D. Gand. and Christakopoulos, P. (2016). Metabolic Engineering of *Fusarium oxysporum* to Improve Its Ethanol-Producing Capability. *Front. Microbiol.* 7:632. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2016.00632.
- [5]. Barnett, H. L., and B.B. Hunter. (1972). *Illustrated genera of imperfect fungi*. Third edition. Burgess publishing company. Minnesota University.
- [6]. Bekheet, S.A., El-Sharabasy, S.F. (2015). Date Palm Status and Perspective in Egypt. In: Al-Khayri, J., Jain, S., Johnson, D. (eds) *Date Palm Genetic Resources and Utilization*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9694-1_3.
- [7]. Selim, M. A., Hassan, E. A., Eletmany, M. R., & Harb, A.-E. A. (2014). Synthesis of New Derivatives of Nicotine, Pyridazine, Cinnoline Compounds via the Reaction of Pyridylhydrazonals with Active Methylene Derivatives. Assiut University 9th International Pharmaceutical Sciences Conference. Presented at the Assiut University 9th International Pharmaceutical Sciences Conference, Faculty of Pharmacy, Assiut, Egypt.
- [8]. Belarbi-Halli, R. and Mangenot, F. (2011). Bayoud disease of date palm: ultrastructure of root infection through pneumatodes. *Canadian Journal of Botany* 64(8):1703-1711, DOI:10.1139/b86-228
- [9]. Benzohra, I. E., Mohamed, M. and Rafik, B. (2015). Bayoud disease of date palm in Algeria: History, epidemiology, and integrated disease management. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. Vol. 14(7), pp. 542-550. DOI: 10.5897/AJBX2014.14292.
- [10]. Booth, C. (1977). *The Genus Fusarium*, Commonwealth Mycological Institute, Ferry Lane, Kew, Surrey, England.p.12
- [11]. Cenis, J.L. (1992). *Nucleic Acids Research*, Vol. 20, No. 9, p. 2380.
- [12]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Fandy, R. F., & Aly, K. I. (2018). Synthesis and characterization of new benzoxazines polymers and their applications. 4th Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-4). Presented at the 4th Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-4), South Valley University, Qena, Egypt.
- [13]. Eletmany, M. R. (2018). Development of New Organic Hole Transport Compounds for high Performances Organic Solar cells. 2nd International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE). Presented at the 2nd International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE), South Valley University, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [14]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Fandy, R. F., & Aly, K. I. (2019). Synthesis and characterization of new benzoxazines polymers and their applications. 5th Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-5). Presented at the 5th Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-5), South Valley University, Qena, Egypt.
- [15]. Cherkaoui El Modafar. (2010). Mechanisms of date palm resistance to Bayoud disease: Current

- [16]. Dinolfo, M.I., Castañares, E., Stenglein, S.A. (2017). Fusarium–plant interaction: state of the art–a review. *Plant Protect. Sci.*, Vol. 53, No. 2: 61–70.
- [17]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Fandy, R. F., & Aly, K. I. (2018). Synthesis and characterization of some new polymers with biological and industrial applications. 2nd Annual Conference of the Faculty of Science. Presented at the 2nd Annual Conference of the Faculty of Science, South Valley University, Qena, Egypt.
- [18]. FAO. Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2022). FAO statistical yearbook.
- [19]. FAO. Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2023). FAO statistical yearbook.
- [20]. Fernandez, Diana; M. Ouinten; A. Tantaoui; J. Geiger; Marie-Jose E Daboussi and T. Langing (1998). Fot 1 Insertions in the *Fusarium oxysporum* F. sp. *albedinis* Genome Provide Diagnostic PCR Targets for Detection of the Date Palm Pathogen. *Applied And Environmental Microbiology*, Vol. 64, No. 2., p. 633-636.
- [21]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Fandy, R. F., & Aly, K. I. (2019). Synthesis and Characterization of Some New Benzoxazine Polymers with Their Industrial Applications. 3rd Annual Conference of the Faculty of Science. Presented at the 3rd Annual Conference of the Faculty of Science, Faculty of Science, South Valley University, Qena, Egypt.
- [22]. Freeman, S. and M. Maymon (2000). Reliable Detection of the Fungal Pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *albedinis*, Causal Agent of Bayoud Disease of Date Palm, Using Molecular Techniques. *Phytoparasitica*, 28(4):341-348.
- [23]. Grattidge, R. and O'Brien, R. G. (1982). Occurrence of a third race of *Fusarium* wilt of tomatoes in Queensland. *Plant Dis* 66:165–166.
- [24]. Leslie, J.F. and B. A. Summerell (2006). *The Fusarium Laboratory Manual*. Iowa, USA.
- [25]. Loutfy, I.E. (2010) Degradation of Date Palm Trees and Date Production in Arab Countries: Causes and Potential Rehabilitation. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 4(8): 3998-4010.
- [26]. Eletmany, M. R. (2019). Development of New Organic Hole Transport Compounds for high Performances Organic Solar cells. 3rd International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE). Presented at the 3rd International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE), South Valley University, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [27]. Nelson, P.E.; T.A. Toussoun and W.F.O. Marasas (1983). *Fusarium Species: An Illustrated Manual for Identification*. Pennsylvania State University Press; University Park, Pennsylvania, USA. pp. 207.
- [28]. Noor Adila, A.K., Farah Diba, A.B., Zamri, Z., Wan Mohtar, W.Y., Aidil, A.H., Mahadi, N.M. and Murad, A.M.A (2007). Comparison of methods for isolating high quality DNA and RNA from an oleaginous fungus *Cunninghamella bainieri* strain 2a1. *Mal. J. Microbiol*, 3(1): 7-13.
- [29]. Saleh, A. A., Sharafaddin, A. H., El_Komy, M. H., Ibrahim, Y. E. and Hamad, Y. K. (2021) Molecular and physiological characterization of *Fusarium* strains associated with different diseases in date palm. *PLoS ONE* 16(7): e0254170. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254170>.
- [30]. Sami S. Adawi, Jiming Jiang & Mohamed A. M. Atia. (2014). Identification of novel sex-specific PCR based markers to distinguish the genders in Egyptian date palm trees. *International Journal of Agricultural Science and Research (IJASR)* ISSN(P): 2250-0057; ISSN(E): 2321-0087 Vol. 4, Issue 5, pp. 45-54.
- [31]. State of knowledge and research prospects. *Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology* 74, 287e294.
- [32]. Harb, A. E. A., & Eletmany, M. R. SYNTHESIS OF NEW DERIVATIVES OF NICOTINE VIA THE REACTION OF ARYLHYDRAZONALS WITH ACTIVE METHYLENE DERIVATIVES.
- [33]. Tsutomu Arie. (2019). *Fusarium* diseases of cultivated plants, control, diagnosis, and molecular and genetic studies. *J. Pestic. Sci.* 44(4), 275–281, DOI: 10.1584/jpestics.J19-03.
- [34]. Tulin Askun. (2018). *Fusarium*: plant diseases, pathogen diversity, genetic diversity, resistance, and molecular markers. ISBN 978-1-78923-319-3. DOI 10.5772/intechopen.69673.
- [35]. Selim, M. A., & Eletmany, M. R. SYNTHESIS OF NEW DERIVATIVES OF NICOTINE, PYRIDAZINE, CINNOLINE COMPOUNDS VIA THE REACTION OF ARYLHYDRAZONALS WITH ACTIVE METHYLENE DERIVATIVES.
- [36]. Woo SL, Zoina A, Gel SG, Lorito M, Nanni B, Scala F, Noviello C, (1996). Characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *phaseoli* by pathogenic races, VCG, RFLPs, and RAPD. *Phytopathology* 86, 966–73.
- [37]. Zhao, B.; j. Yan; S. Zhang; X. Liu and Z. Gao (2014). Phylogeny and pathogenicity of *Fusarium* ssp. isolates from greenhouse melon soil in Liaoning province. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 21:374-379.
- [38]. Selim, M. A., Hassan, E. A., Harb, A.-E. A., & Eletmany, M. R. (2015). Synthesis of Some New Derivatives of Nicotine via the Reaction of Arylhydrazonals with Active Methylene Derivatives. 13th IBN SINA International Conference on Pure and Applied Heterocyclic Chemistry. Presented at the 13th IBN SINA International Conference on Pure and Applied Heterocyclic Chemistry, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [39]. Hassan, N. M., & Eletmany, M. R. (2015). Baubiology Science between Theory and Application. 2nd Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-2). Presented at the 2nd Young Researchers of Egyptian Universities Conference (YREUC-2), South Valley University, Qena-Luxor, Egypt.

- [40]. Selim, M. A., Hassan, E. A., Harb, A.-E. A., & Eletmany, M. R. (2016). Some spectral studies of New Derivatives of Nicotine, Pyridazine, Cinnoline Compounds. 7th International Conference on Optical Spectroscopy, Laser and Their Applications. Presented at the 7th International Conference on Optical Spectroscopy, Laser and Their Applications, NRC, Cairo, Egypt.
- [41]. Eletmany, M. R. (2017). Development of New Organic Hole Transport Compounds for high Performances Dye-sensitized Solar cells. 1st International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE). Presented at the 1st International Conference on Natural Resources and Renewable Energy (ICNRRE), South Valley University, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [42]. Aly, K. I., Fandy, R. F., Hassan, E. A., & Eletmany, M. R. (2018). Synthesis and characterization of novel 2-substituted 1,3- benzoxazines monomers and studies their polymerization. 13th IBN SINA International Conference on Pure and Applied Heterocyclic Chemistry. Presented at the 13th IBN SINA International Conference on Pure and Applied Heterocyclic Chemistry, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [43]. Ramadan Abd Allah Eletmany M. (2017). Reaction of 3-oxo-arylhydrazonal with active methylene nitriles synthesis of heterocyclic compounds via the reaction of 3-oxo-arylhydrazonal derivatives with active methylene nitriles (1. Auflage). LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing. Retrieved October 14, 2023, from <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:101:1-201707172849>.
- [44]. Barqi, M. M., Abdellah, I. M., Eletmany, M. R., Ali, N. M., Elhenawy, A. A., & Abd El Latif, F. M. (2023). Synthesis, Characterization, Bioactivity Screening and Computational Studies of Diphenyl-malonohydrazides and Pyridines Derivatives. *ChemistrySelect*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.202203913>
- [45]. Abdellah, I. M., Eletmany, M. R., Abdelhamid, A. A., Alghamdi, H. S., Abdalla, A. N., Elhenawy, A. A., & Latif, F. M. A. E. (2023). One-Pot Synthesis of Novel Poly-Substituted 3-Cyanopyridines: Molecular Docking, Antimicrobial, Cytotoxicity, and DFT/TD-DFT Studies. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1289, 135864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2023.135864>
- [46]. Eletmany, M. R., Aziz Albalawi, M., Alharbi, R. A. K., Elamary, R. B., Harb, A. E.-F. A., Selim, M. A., ... Abdellah, I. M. (2023). Novel arylazo nicotinate derivatives as effective antibacterial agents: Green synthesis, molecular modeling, and structure-activity relationship studies. *Journal of Saudi Chemical Society*, 27(3), 101647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jscs.2023.101647>
- [47]. Abdellah, I. M., Eletmany, M. R., & El-Shafei, A. (2023). Exploring the impact of electron acceptor tuning in D- π -A'- π -A photosensitizers on the photovoltaic performance of acridine-based DSSCs: A DFT/TDDFT perspective. *Materials Today Communications*, 35, 106170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106170>
- [48]. Ashar, A., Bhutta, Z. A., Shoaib, M., Alharbi, N. K., Fakhar-e-Alam, M., Atif, M., ... Ezzat Ahmed, A. (2023). Cotton fabric loaded with ZnO nanoflowers as a photocatalytic reactor with promising antibacterial activity against pathogenic E. coli. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 16(9), 105084. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabj.2023.105084>
- [49]. Ashar, A., Qayyum, A., Bhatti, I. A., Aziz, H., Bhutta, Z. A., Abdel-Maksoud, M. A., Saleem, M. H. and Eletmany, M. R., (2023). "Photo-Induced Super-Hydrophilicity of Nano-Calcite @ Polyester Fabric: Enhanced Solar Photocatalytic Activity against Imidacloprid", *ACS Omega*, 8(39), 37522-35737 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.3c02987>
- [50]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Fandy, R. F., & Aly, K. I. (2019). Synthesis and characterization of Novel 2-substituted 1,3-benzoxazines monomers and studies their Polymerization. 14th International Conference on Chemistry and its Role in Development (ICCRD-2019). Presented at the 14th International Conference on Chemistry and its Role in Development (ICCRD-2019), Mansoura University, Hurghada, Egypt.
- [51]. Eletmany, M. R., Hassan, E. A., Harb, A. E.-F. A., & Selim, M. A. (2017). Reaction of 3-Oxo-arylhydrazonal derivatives with active methylene nitriles. London: LAMPERT Academic Publishing. <https://www.worldcat.org/isbn/9783330328730>
- [52]. Abdel Aziz, E. M., Elmorshely, H. A., Abd-Elkader, A. S., Haridi, Mostafa A. (2022). "Causes of End Stage Renal Disease in patients undergoing regular hemodialysis in Assiut University Hospital", *Sapporo igaku zasshi. The Sapporo medical journal* 55(12):12.
- [53]. Abdellah, I. M., Yildirim, E., & El-Shafei, A. (2023). Low-cost novel X-shaped hole transport materials for efficient perovskite solar cells: Molecular modelling of the core and schiff base effects on photovoltaic and photophysical properties. *MATERIALS CHEMISTRY AND PHYSICS*, 296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2022.127188>